

Progress report from Working Group 3 ‘Open science monitoring with scholarly content providers’ - March 2026

1. General information

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Objectives:

- Increase the involvement of a variety of scholarly content providers in open science monitoring initiatives
- Increase the availability of results and methods of open science monitoring with scholarly content providers
- Stimulate new initiatives, research, and collaborations that advance and improve the monitoring of open science with scholarly content

The scope of the group includes monitoring of both outputs (e.g. open access publications, data and code sharing) and outcomes of open science (e.g. reuse, societal impact) that relate to scholarly content. The key audience for this Working Group (WG) is scholarly content providers, which we described as organizations and/or platforms that host scholarly content and create metadata for scholarly objects and/or connections between the object they host and other scholarly objects.

2. Summary of the group's activities and outputs

In order to gather a broad overview of the current state of practices among scholarly content providers, the WG completed a survey circulated to OSMI members and colleagues. The survey received 51 full responses and results were [disseminated via OSMI](#) and also summarized in a [blog post on Upstream](#).

Informed by the survey results and collaborative group discussion, the WG distilled two areas of work:

1. [Benefits, evidence & implementation considerations for scholarly content providers](#)

This focused on developing an overview of what open science monitoring is done by scholarly content providers, their motivations, implementation approaches and resourcing needs, with information relevant to both expand existing monitoring and for newcomers.

A dedicated subgroup has explored the areas of information required and identified case studies as a suitable approach to collect and showcase information about existing practices by scholarly content providers. The subgroup has documented the information to be collected for the case studies and identified a set of scholarly content providers to approach, and will soon pursue collection of information.

2. Open science indicators

This area focuses on developing recommendations for indicators for scholarly content providers to monitor open science, including best practices and necessary infrastructure and open information for indicators.

Informed by the survey and expert input by members, the WG defined three categories of indicators: enablers of monitoring by content providers, output indicators, outcome indicators. The group has developed a framework for the enablers and indicators in each category, and documented the information each indicator provides to the content provider, and the approach to track each indicator. The group is finalizing the information associated with each enabler and indicator.

3. Challenges, upcoming activities, deliverables, timeline and working group duration

As the areas of work became more clearly defined, we established subgroups with separate focuses. A challenge that arose was ensuring these two groups could progress without duplicating efforts while keeping the full WG updated. To address this, we discussed and documented the scope of each subgroup early on, created shared documents to track discussions and keep completed items accessible to all WG members, and used monthly WG meetings to share updates and invite feedback on the two areas.

Our next steps will include the collection of information toward the case studies by the 'Benefits, evidence & implementation considerations for scholarly content providers' subgroup and creating resources based on this, and a report outlining the framework for enablers and indicators and the recommendations by the 'Open science indicators subgroup'. We anticipate having the deliverable by the indicators subgroup by May 2026. The case studies and further resources from the other subgroup will be completed over the next months, and we expect to complete the full WG activities by Q4 2026.